

Human Capital And Servant Leadership to Improve Service Climate At Public Service Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 20, 2025</p> <p>Accepted: April 23, 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Human Capital; Servant Leadership; Service Climate; Public Service; Service Quality; Civil Servant</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15270693</p>	<p><i>This study focuses on service quality from a mere competing instrument to that of the basic core of the service concept in human capital. Service quality is a measure of how well the service level delivered matches people/ customers expectations. It's generated by developing service climate in organization. Service climate is the shared employee perceptions of the policies, practices, and the behaviors that get rewarded, supported, and expected with regard to customer service and customer service quality. Service Climate antecedent can be divided by personal factor as human capital and job factor as servant leadership. Human Capital is a set of sum knowledge, experience, skills, attitude, value, other personal attributes which can contribute positively to organization. Servant leadership is a philosophy and set of practices that enriches the lives of individuals, builds better organizations for caring persons, the more able and the less able serving each other. The study was conducted at West Java Province-Indonesia. By using cluster random sampling technique, 200 respondents is classified as sample of study. The population study was a Civil Servant at Government who occupied the Head and supervisor of the division at 32 workunits that provide public services to the community. Based on statistical tests, the study found that the Human Capital and Servant Leadership partially or simultaneously have significant effect on the Service Climate. Service Climate has significant impact on the public service performance. These findings prove that to develop the performance of public services, can be done by developing service climate. Service climate influenced by Human Capital and Servant Leadership in the organization.</i></p>

Introduction

Public servant, is not deniable, is a major important role in Indonesian government. This brings out issues of changes, developments and improvements of public service performance by all countries in their competing government bureaucracy (Rainer Rohdewold, 2008); (Pramono, 2014). **Indonesia itself has** started the issues of change in and developing public service performance since the fall of dominance Suharto rezim at 1998 by releasing a pack of reformation policies through the statement of law constitution at Undang-Undang Nomor 22 Tahun 1999 about local government and other law statements changes (Soesilo, 2016)). Unfortunately, the reformation has not been priority in each period of leadership nor in central government or local (Prasojo, 2007).

Low level of public service performance can be seen on Governance Assessment Survey result in 2006 of 10 Indonesian provinces, showed that people perception about public service is extremely severe (SJORAIDA & Anwar, 2017), such as West Java Province. Other researches by Budi (2007) also showed no difference result, where level of public service performance is founded low and not optimal (dalam (SJORAIDA & Anwar, 2017).

There are behaviors of people that will support service government in achieving goals. These behaviors are affected by governmental environment and also by individuals of government staff itself. The role of management in using their human capital will promote more productive and positive behaviors of individuals. Human capital is a driving factor of other resources. The importance of studying human capital showed that organizing human capital is important too.

The deepest meaning of leadership is actually the efforts to affect people, meanwhile in Indonesia by noticing the law cases of public officials (and also in academical sector) tend to put individual and/or group interest before nation (though the reason was for nation). This can be seen on common profiles of public official leaders in Indonesia. Based on earlier researches (2013) of public officials in 15 local government (province/city/district) of West Java, resulted in common leadership characteristics of structural leaders in several areas in West Java, which is : 1) 86,7% (26 persons) agreed that structural position election has not been

based on competencies, and still effected by individual and/or group interests, not by transparant election; 2) 97% (29 persons) agreed that most government officer that closed to those who has power would be promoted to structural position, so that they would use any ways (including unproper ways) to achieve those positions; 3) 76,67% (23 persons) chose that in certain ways leaders used their power to insist their subordinates to do things that is not allowed by the rules, and these subordinates can say “no” because of such reason like loyalty and negative impact on career (e.g mutation).

By analysing human capital, leadership and how this would establish positive service climate on district government and central government, the result will provide benefits in creating optimum public service. Through observation, interviews and analysing data, there are some conditionsthat are found in government:

- Dissatisfying service of Civil Identification (ID) public service (research by(Heywood, Harahap, & Aryani, 2011). There are 4 (four) administrative villages and 4 (four) subdistricts resulted that there are no clear information about when and how the technical practices of electric ID can be delivered.
- Monitoring system of changes in allocation of land or inappropriate development of buildings and houses, are still weak.
- Satisfaction Society Index in B city city towards service of public servant are still scored 60,85 (dissatisfied). The service is experienced as slow and uncertain.
- Health service in West Java Province-Indonesiais still dissatisfying.

Based on conditions above, researchers tried to analyze the performance of public servant performance, in relation to Service Climate perceived by staff, and how this is effected by human capital as individual capacity of public servant and by service leadership of supervisors/managers.

THEORETICAL STUDY

2.1. Human Capital

Humancapitalis individual assets as worker that consist of knowledge, experience, skill, attitude, value, and other personal attrubutes that has added value to organization (Peterson & Spiker, 2005). Human Capitalconsists of*Psychological Capital, Intellectual Capital, Emotional Capital, andSocial Capital*, or known as *PIES human capital*, as described by scheme below :

From the scheme above, the component of *human capital* can be described as :

- a. *Psychological Capital*. A psychological capital that contribute to individual success as an employee in organization. Including confidence/self efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience.
- b. *Intellectual Capital*. An intellectual capital of organization that consists of commitment to organization and employee’s job competencies. Such as experiences, skills, knowledges, and capabilities.
- c. *Emotional Capital*. An emotional capital that contribute to individual success as an employee. Including self awareness, motivation, self regulation, social skill, and social awareness.
- d. *Social Capital*. A social capital that contribute to individual success as an employee, such as networking, trust, and civic norms.

2.2. Servant Leadership

Servant Leadership concept was established from a sequence of experiences and philosophical thoughts about management by (Krogt & Arnhem, 2015). In *Servant Leadership- a journey into the Nature of legitimate Power & Greatness* (2002:3), Edwards Deming stated that 90% of problems in organization were caused by poor system, not human. Greenleaf in (Krogt & Arnhem, 2015) said that great leaders are those who act as a “servant”, who put others’ needs (employees, customers, and community) as priority.

The Center for Servant Leadership in *The Pastorall Institute* of Georgia defined *servant leadership* as a long journey of life that include self discovery, a passion to serve people and commitment to lead others. *Servant-leaders* are a person who will continually strive to be trusted, self-aware, humble, caring, visionary, empowering, relational, competent, good stewards, and a community builders. (Spears, 2010) has identified 10 characteristics of *servant leaders* as below :

- 1) *Listening* : focus on listening to identify and clarify group’s needs and desires.
- 2) *Empathy* : try to understand other’s feeling and emotion.
- 3) *Healing* : strive to avoid himself and others from failure and misery
- 4) *Awareness* : well aware of his own capabilities and limitations.
- 5) *Persuasion* : more focused on persuasion than authority of power in making decision and affecting people.
- 6) *Conceptualization* : give time and efforts to develop based on conceptual thinking. Servant-leader always looks for balance between focus on day-to-day short term and long term conceptual orientation.
- 7) *Foresight* : has an ability to foresee the result in future that associated by recent condition or behaviors.
- 8) *Stewardship* : always think that they are here to serve people, manage people and other resources.
- 9) *Commitment to the growth of people* : commitment to everyone, including those people that are not related to their job role. *Servant-leader* commits to “power” the community.
- 10) *Building community* : create *sense of community* in and/or outside organization.

2.3. Service Climate

Schneider & White (dalam (Spears, 2010)) defined service climate as: “*Service climate as the shared employee perceptions of the policies, practices, and the behaviors that get rewarded, supported, and expected with regard to customer service and customer service quality*”. While Kelly (1992, in (Pulwarty & Redmond, 1997) defined service climate as: “*A set of descriptive characteristics concerning service delivery and service quality that differentiate an organization from others and influence the service –related behavior of individuals in organization*”.

In relation to *Organizational Service Orientation* (Pulwarty & Redmond, 1997) defined service climate as : “*service climate, which is a very similar concept (with service orientation), has been identified as negatively related to the owners service values (the degree to which owners valued innovativeness, attentiveness, outcome-orientation, aggressiveness, support, and decisiveness) in the small business environment*.”

Based on those definitions, we can conclude that service climate is a shared perceptions that is developed by the employees about policies, practices, procedures, and behaviors that is rewarded, supported, and expected, to serve customer and to achieve good customer service quality. In other terms, service climate showed how much internal functions in organizations are focused on service.

According to the statement, it can be assumed if organization is concerned with the way service is given and other things that related to service orientation and values, these will lead to the creation of employee perception that is favourable towards organization. Schneider stated there are 2 basic dimensions in creating service climate and 3 other dimensions in service climate, they are :

- 1) *Internal Service* : quality of service that is perceived by employees and managers to enable them doing their job (Hallowell & Shclesinger (2000)
- 2) *Climate for Work Facilitation* : perceived support and facilitation by employees to do their job. Including (a) efforts to eliminate job obstacles ((Burke, Borucki, & Kaufman, 2002); (Schneider, White, & Paul, 1998) dan (b) monitoring behaviors (e.g giving feedback and information; (Bowen & Schneider, 2014) and (c) Human Resource Management policies (Schneider et al., 1998)

There are other 3 dimensions of service climate according to Schneider :

- 1) *Customer Orientation* : degrees of how organization focused on delivering customer’s needs and expectations to get higher service quality.
- 2) *Managerial Practices* : reflects mid-managers’ behavior to support and reward those who deliver high service quality.
- 3) *Customer Feedback* : practices of getting and using feedback from customer about service quality.

2.4. Public Service Performance

Public service performance in this research is using Service Quality concept. (Shahin, 2010) is defined service quality as an indicator of how well the service quality was performed can be as expected by customer. If the perceived service is as expected service, then the service quality would be perceived as positive, and vice versa.

In 1985, (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985) described that there is 4 (four) service quality gap that is :

1. Gap between customer expectation and management perception (*Knowledge gap*).
2. Gap between management perception towards customer expectation and service quality specifications (*standards gap*).
3. Gap between service quality specifications and service delivery (*delivery gap*)
4. Gap between service delivery and external communication (*communications gap*)

(Parasuraman et al., 1985) stated that SERVQUAL model has been represent the assumptions of dimension of public service. Service process in public birocracy is actually not as complicated as perceived. Each procedures has been particularly arranged in clear and defined rules and SOP (standard operating procedures). What to be noticed here is how the attitude and behaviors of public servant in delivering the service to community.

Researcher are using dimension from (Parasuraman et al., 1985) because it has accomodated the aspects of public service that are needed, they are 1) *Tangibles* can be found on physical performance of facilities, equipments, employees, and communication tools. These conditions can be found in government birocracy and be one of the most attentive factor in government.; 2) *Reliability*, showed by the capabilities and anticipations of public servant in giving promises related to job accomplishment. This aspect is also found in every public services where service level agreement has been set; 3) *Responsiveness* is the readiness and willingness of public servant to deliver service as expected by customer. 4) *Assurance* is found in public servant capability to assure customer and have their trust; 5) *Empathy* is the main factor in service, it is the willingness to understand customers' needs.

2.5. Framework of Study

Low level of public service performance government is a reflection of : (1) public servant have less awareness about their duty and responsibilities; (2) system, procedures, controls, and work methods are not optimal that can disrupt public service performance; (3) the organization of service task has not been harmonized; (4) Unoptimal quality of public servant in delivering service tasks; and (5) lack of availabilities in service infrastructures, many losses of time, slow working, and delayed problem solving (Bagia, Cipta, & Suarmanayasa, 2019). These conditions create a gap in expectation of public service quality in local governments.

The condition of human capital and servant leadership conceptually have strong impact on service climate. With no good human capital and servant leadership, service climate would not be established properly, which affect on dissatisfaction of public service performance. If service climate perceived as positive and favorable by the employees, this condition may promote employees to perform high level of service quality. As decribed by sheme below :

Figure 2. Framework of Research

3. RESEARCH METHODS

Approach on this research is *hypothetico deductive method* that analyze actual phenomenon by using theoretical framework to define research hypothesis based on initial assumptions of phenomenon and theories. The research design is using *causal research non experimental approach*, to understand causal relationship between independent variable and dependent variable, without any interventions into the subject.

Population

The population in this research is Civil Servant in West Java Province. There are 557 persons (head section and supervisor) in this population. There are 32 work units that directly serve to community.

Sampling

This research is using *clusterrandomsampling*. The steps are :

1. Classify Civil Servant (PNS) into different work units
2. Set group sample of head section and supervisor section to appraise leadership of head division
3. Set sample using different cluster

Table 1. Sample Research

Total Sample 200

No	SKPD	SAMPLE	No	SKPD	SAMPLE
1	BAPPEDA	5	17	Satpol PP	6
2	Disperindakop	6	18	BPLH	6
3	DPPPJU	5	19	Kapermas	3
4	SETDA	5	20	BPPT	6
5	Disdik	9	21	Kec.Mustikajaya	8
6	Dinsos	6	22	Kec. Jatisampurna	5
7	Disdukcapil	7	23	Kec. B city Barat	7
8	Dinsih	4	24	Kec. B city Timur	8
9	Dishub	9	25	Kec. B city Selatan	4
10	Dispera	10	26	Kec. B city Utara	8
11	Distako	10	27	Kec. Rawalumbu	5
12	Disnaker	6	28	Kec. PondokMelati	6
13	Disdikmarta	9	29	Kec. Jatiasih	4
14	Dinkes	8	30	Perpustakaan Daerah	3
15	RSUD	9	31	Podbudpar	3
16	BPPAKB	4	32	Dispenda	4
	Total	112		Total	88

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothetical testing showed results as described below ::

Main Hypothesis : "Human Capital and Servant Leadership influence the public service performance through Service Climate of Civil Servant Performance"

Table 2. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis Model	Sig.	Prob. Value	F	Conclusion
X1 and X2 towards Y1	0.00	0.05	51.087	X1 and X2 significantly influence Y1
Y1 towards Y2	0.00	0.05	109.348	and affect Y2

This showed that *Human Capital* and *Servant Leadership* influence Service Climate and also have impact on Public Service Performance.

Sub Hypothesis 1 : "Human Capital and Servant Leadership influence partially and simultaneously Service Climate of Civil Servant of B city Government"

Table 3. Determination

Variable	Coeff Beta	R ²	Sig.	F	t-hit.	Conclusion
X1 and X2 simultaneously towards Y1	-	0.342	0.00	51.087	-	X1 and X2 simultaneously and significantly influence Y1 Contribution = 34.2%
X1 partially towards Y1	0.350	-	0.00		5.737	X1 partially and significantly influence Y1 Contribution = 12.3%
X2 partially towards Y1	0.368	-	0.00		6.031	X2 partially and significantly influence Y1

As statistical result above, Human Capital and Servant Leadership variable are significantly influence Service Climate, in both partially and simultaneously. Partially, Human Capital influence Service Climate significantly with coefficient 0.32, which means that Human Capital can significantly explain 12.3% variabilities of Service Climate variable, while the rest is influenced by other factors. In the other hand, Servant Leadership also partially influence Service Climate, significantly with coefficient 0.368, which means that Servant Leadership can describe 13,5% variabilities of Service Climate, while the rest is influenced by other factors.

Sub Hypothesis-2: “Service Climate influence Public Service Performance of Civil Servant of B city Government”

Table 4. Hypthotesis Testing

Variable	Coeff Beta	R ²	Sig.	F	t-hit	Conclusion
Y1 towards Y2	0.596	0.356	0.00	109.348	10.457	Y1 significantly influence Y2 Contribution = 35.6%

The result showed that Service Climate influence Public Service Performance with contribution 35.6%.

Figure3. Hypothetical Testing Framework 1

Note : X1 = Human Capital
 X2 = Servant Leadership
 Y1 = Service Climate
 Y2 = Public Service Performance

As statistical data showed that *Human Capital* and *Servant Leadership* significantly influence Public Service Performance through Service Climate. It is shown that Human Capital variable and Servant Leadership variable partially and simultaneously influence Service Climate. Partially, Human Capital influence Service Climate with coefficient 0.350, or in other terms, the contribution toward Service Climate is 12,3%. In the other hand, Servant Leadership partially influence Service Climate with coefficient 0.368, or it can be said that the contribution toward service climate is 13.5%.

The result showed that the contribution of Servant Leadership in influencing Service Climate is almost the same contribution of Human Capital toward Service Climate. This means that the servant leadership of managers in B city Government have balance influence with the Human Capital in Civil Servant individuals. It promotes the establishment of positive or favorable service climate. If we see on the simultan influence of Human Capital and Servant Leadership towards Service Climate, this effect is actually greater, with 34.2% effects. In other words, compared to contributions of each influences of Human Capital and Servant Leadership toward Service Climate, the effect of both variables simultaneously towards service climate is higher.

Based on Kurt Lewin concept at (Esa, Muda, Ibrahim, & Mansor, 2017) that stated: $B = f(P, E)$ where B is *Behavior*, P is *Person* and E is *Environment*, then with this formula showed that the influence of individual capacity (internal aspects), in this research is Human Capital of Civil Servant, and the influence of environment (external aspects), which is Servant Leadership “perceived” by Civil Servant of B city Government, have same strong impact on developing Service Climate. But, both aspects (Human Capital and Servant Leadership) when function simultaneously would be a great power to influence Service Climate changes.

Related to Human Capital influences, as shown by path analysis, Human Capital as individual resources of Civil Servant B city Government, have significantly influence, partially and simultaneously with Servant Leadership, toward Service Climate.

Quality of human resources in form of Human Capital in Civil Servant individuals can be analyzed through the process with how the employees contribute in creating service climate by implementing all service policies, including maintaining job orientation that focused on customer (internal and community).

Petterson and Spiker (2005) stated that *Human Capital* adalah individual asset as an employee that consist of knowledge, experience, skills, attitude, values and other personal attributes that have added value to organization. Related to service climate, the added value is service behavior that gained from shared perception in organization, department, or group, on how employees are expected to behave and perform service behavior in any situation and community's needs.

Based on the statement above, we can see clearly that the influence of human capital and servant leadership in promoting high public service performance can be achieved by creating service climate. The model showed that the external influence, that is servant leadership by managers, has same amount of contributions as human capital influence, in creating positive or favorable service climate.

In partial influence of Servant Leadership towards Service Climate, dimensions that contribute the most in developing servant leadership which promote positive service climate are *Listening*, *Conceptualization* and *Building Community*. It can be said that according to the respondents, their leaders/managers are willing to listen to their needs as the operator of their job, which mostly they serve community in direct. Leaders or managers have clear concept or program for society and show interest and attention in developing internal and external community of B city government organization.

Climate approach in work environment analyze organizational behavior through subject's point of view, where employee has tendencies to form their perception by considering how the organization's day-to-day process and by the goal that are perceived through how they run the organization (Zolghadr & Asgari, 2016). Public service government is originated to serve community. They have responsibilities to create fair and favorable environment for community. Civil servant in this situation need to adapt with any environmental changes. Besides adaptive, civil servant also need to develop themselves to match the expectation of each changes.

Efforts on assuring rules and operation of service task have been done by the government in many ways to promote civil servant performance such as laws of disciplinary for civil servants, trainings and seminars, improvement of employee's wealth (e.g remuneration systems, pension rights, retirement and promotion system). Nevertheless, these efforts have not shown any results yet. There are still complaints from community through mass media. Such as inappropriate rate of administrative, illegal extortion by service officer, slow response of registered civil ID process, illegal administrative process by using third party, and others. These conditions showed that the level of public service performance is still low. Through descriptive data, even though public service performance are scored as high enough and high, there are still few public servant that scored as low enough. Schneider stated that in order to find out the level of satisfaction of community as customer of public service (in this situation Public Service Government), it is enough by knowing how the service climate is by the public servant Government. If the service climate is perceived as positive or favorable, then it can assure that the service quality is good or favorable too.

This research resulted in description of service climate that 13% of civil servants perceived that the service climate organization in West Java Province government is quite negative. This means that there are several people who experienced less supportive for them to do their job in serving community. The highest dimension that scored as quite negative is *Internal Service* (32,5%), which means there are still public servant who perceived that the service between working units in West Java Province government are still low, not quite supportive in delivering good quality service.

Service climate basically represent the perception of employees about internal organization functions that focused on service quality. (Schneider et al., 1998) explained that when employee feels rewarded by delivering good service quality, perceives that the management give time and resources to support good service quality, and when the employee receives trainings that support them to interact effectively with different customers, then positive service climate will be attached on those experiences.

The highest dimension in creating service climate is *Customer Orientation*. It is how the organization focus on good service quality in achieving community needs and expectations. This means how far the service orientation of (Bowen & Schneider, 2014) in

delivering good service quality so that the community are able to use their services effectively and integrated. Orientation to customer (community) requires social competence of individuals to understand what are needed and interpersonal skills to deliver those needs.

Other dimension that also determine service climate is *Managerial Practice*. Managerial Practice is managerial behaviors and practices that is conducted in order to support and appreciate service quality behaviors. It includes reward and recognition from management to employee who delivers service quality as expected by Government. This service behavior is reflection of Social Competence in Emotional Capital that consists of social skill and social awareness.

Social awareness is an ability that depends on emotional awareness to understand and be empathy on other people's feelings, so that one can perform genuine service behavior and as expected. *Social awareness* consists of ability to understand people emotions, perspectives, and give attention to what other needs (empathy), ability to understand group and organization situation, and also the group cohesiveness, group decisions, and political situation in group, and also the ability to anticipate, identify and to meet other people's needs (service orientation).

In relation to the role and impact of servant leadership, as (Schneider et al., 1998), this research showed that manager as leader presents servant leadership behaviors that not only motivate their subordinates to perform good public service, but also as a role model that inspires their subordinates to perform good service behavior.

The role of leaders in creating and developing service climate are also found on earlier research by (Price, 1972), stated that one of the role of leader in developing service climate is to create and design policies, programs, and procedures that aligned with service values in organization and assure rewards for those who implement service policies to achieve organizational service goal.

Partial influences of Servant Leadership toward Service Climate showed that the dimensions with high contributions in creating servant leadership so that it can promote positive service climate are *Listening, Conceptualization* and *Building Community*. It can be concluded that according to public servant of West Java Province government, their leaders are willing to listen to their needs in order to serve public. Leaders have clear service concepts and programs to serve public and to show interest in developing internal and external communication of West Java Province government organization.

5. CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

Based on results, the conclusion of the research are :

1. *Human Capital* and *Servant Leadership* partially and simultaneously influence service climate.
2. Service climate positively influences Public Service Performance. This result showed that when employees perceive high enough support, reward and expectation to deliver high quality of service to internal and external customer, it will effect on the level of service quality that is delivered. They feel that they have delivered service with enthusiastic, energetic, on time, and as expected by the customer.
3. *Human Capital* of the employees are Quite High (78%). It showed that public servant of West Java Province government have quite good knowledge, experience, skill, attitude, value and other personal attributes that can be added value to West Java Province government.
4. *Servant Leadership* of the employees are also Quite High (70%). This means that leaders' behavior in city B Government are perceived as quite "servant", that put others' needs (including employees' needs) as priority, take holistic approach into work, and have sense of community and togetherness in decision making.
5. Service climate of employees are Quite Positive (78%). It showed that employees perception of organization service condition to customer (internal and external) are quite positive (including policies, practices, procedures, and behaviors that are rewarded and expected in service delivery).
6. Public service performances are Quite High (78%). It showed that the level of service delivered is quite as expected by community, especially in Tangible aspects (physical service performance). It can be found on physical performance of facilities, equipments, employees and communication infrastructure.

5.2 Recommendation

1. Birocracy reformation in Indonesia is created to perform good governance, by developing strategic role of public servant officer in order to deliver high quality of service to community. Public service must be done professionally, and it is work orientation for public servant officer, including West Java Province government. Improvement on work orientation based on good service quality is a short term goal that needs to be implemented in West Java Province government framework.
2. In implementation of *Good Governance*, good service quality for public becomes important for accountability. Effort on public service performance in West Java Province government are must be improved, especially on responsiveness and empathy of employees. Responsiveness means readiness and willingness of

public servant to serve as expected by community. Meanwhile, empathy is an ability to understand community needs.

3. Service climate of West Java Province government is still needs to improve through increased using of Customer feedback, that is practices on collecting and using feedback from community on how good service quality that is delivered. Direct questionnaire and suggestion box can be used as tools for primary evaluation in increasing service quality of B city Government to community.
4. Effort on increasing servant leadership in West Java Province government can be done through improvement of employees' stewardship. It is an assumption that employee's role is to serve community. It is related to employee's role as community servant who has responsibility to perform service orientation to community. Increased orientation as community servant needs to be implemented in order to improve servant leadership.
5. *Human Capital* of employees can be increased by improving social capital of employees. That is, the values of sharing in each member of organization, the organization of roles in organizational structure which is reflected on personal relationships, trustworthiness between members, and responsibilities, so that the organization can function not as a group of individuals.

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